

1 **Tpi1 activation in ulcerative colitis.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 Evidence supporting function of isomerase enzymes with influence on allergic responses in UC.

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8 Citations

9 1. Pekel, G. and Ari, F., 2020. Therapeutic targeting of cancer metabolism with triosephosphate
10 isomerase. *Chemistry & biodiversity*, 17(5), p.e2000012.

11 2. Liu, P., Sun, S.J., Ai, Y.J., Feng, X., Zheng, Y.M., Gao, Y., Zhang, J.Y., Zhang, L., Sun, Y.P., Xiong,
12 Y. and Lin, M., 2022. Elevated nuclear localization of glycolytic enzyme TPI1 promotes lung
13 adenocarcinoma and enhances chemoresistance. *Cell Death & Disease*, 13(3), p.205.

14 3. Duan, Y., Li, J., Wang, F., Wei, J., Yang, Z., Sun, M., Liu, J., Wen, M., Huang, W., Chen, Z. and Lu,
15 Z., 2021. Protein modifications throughout the lung cancer proteome unravel the cancer-specific regulation
16 of glycolysis. *Cell Reports*, 37(12).